

QUANTITATIVE AND QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE ALTERATIONS IN THE ULTRASTRUCTURE OF MAMMALIAN ADRENAL CORTEX GLAND CAUSED BY THE VENEZUELAN BLACK RATTLESNAKE (*Crotalus pifanorum*) VENOM

ANÁLISIS CUANTITATIVO Y CUALITATIVO DE LAS ALTERACIONES ULTRAESTRUCTURALES DE LA CORTEZA DE LA GLÁNDULA ADRENAL DE MAMÍFEROS CAUSADA POR EL VENENO DE LA SERPIENTE DE CASCABEL NEGRA (*Crotalus pifanorum*)

HÉCTOR J. FINOL¹, ESTEFANIE GARCIA-LUNARDI¹, ROSCHMAN GONZÁLEZ¹, ELDA E. SÁNCHEZ², ALEXIS RODRÍGUEZ-ACOSTA^{3,*}

¹Universidad Central de Venezuela, Facultad de Ciencias, Centro de Microscopía Electrónica, Caracas, Venezuela,

²Texas A&M University-Kingsville, National Natural Toxins Research Center, Department of Chemistry, Kingsville, Texas, USA,

³Universidad Central de Venezuela, Facultad de Medicina, Instituto Anatómico, Laboratorio de Inmunología y Ultraestructura, Caracas, Venezuela

*Correspondence: Alexis Rodríguez-Acosta , E-mail: rodriguez-acosta1946@yahoo.es

ABSTRACT

The venom of the black rattlesnake, *Crotalus pifanorum*, contains proteolytic enzymes, peptidases, proteinases, phospholipases and neurotoxins resulting in cytotoxic and neurotoxic effects. In addition, the venom similarly acts on adrenal glands of mice, as it was observed in the present study. The basic structures of the cortex cells from the glands are typical of steroid-producing cells. It has little rough endoplasmic reticulum, but abundant smooth endoplasmic reticulum, where numerous lipid inclusions and mitochondria usually rounded with tubular cristae were observed. From 3 until 24 h after the venom injection, mitochondria, smooth endoplasmic reticulum, nuclear structure and microvasculature damages could be observed. This venom is highly toxic for the adrenal glands. The present results will help the physicians in evaluating the function of these glands in order to avoid fatal outcomes due to an acute suprarenal insufficiency. To our knowledge, this is the first report of adrenal gland damage in mice caused by the injection of *C. pifanorum* venom. Our results advise that adrenal cortex lesions may be significant in the envenoming etiopathogenesis caused by this venom.

KEY WORDS: Cytotoxicity, mitochondria, endoplasmic reticulum, snake, transmission electron microscopy.

RESUMEN

El veneno de la serpiente cascabel negra, *Crotalus pifanorum*, tiene efectos citotóxicos y neurotóxicos. Pero además, actúa de manera similar en la glándula suprarrenal, como se observó en el presente estudio. Contiene enzimas proteolíticas, peptidasas, proteinasas, fosfolipasas y neurotoxinas. La estructura básica de las células de la corteza de esta glándula es típica de las células productoras de esteroides. Tiene poco retículo endoplasmático rugoso, pero abundante retículo endoplasmático liso, donde se observaron numerosas inclusiones lipídicas y mitocondrias, generalmente redondeadas con crestas tubulares. Desde las 3 hasta las 24 h de la inyección de veneno, se pudieron observar intensos daños en mitocondrias, retículo endoplasmático liso, estructura nuclear y en la microvasculatura. Este veneno es altamente tóxico para las glándulas suprarrenales. Los resultados actuales permitirán alertar a los médicos para evaluar la función de esta glándula, a fin de evitar resultados fatales, debido a una insuficiencia suprarrenal aguda. Según nuestra información, este es el primer informe sobre daños en la glándula suprarrenal de ratones, causado por la inyección de veneno de *C. pifanorum*. Nuestros resultados indican que las lesiones de la corteza suprarrenal pueden ser significativas en la grave etiopatogenia causada por este veneno.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Citotoxicidad, mitocondrias, retículo endoplasmático, serpiente, microscopía electrónica de transmisión.

INTRODUCTION

Venezuela, being a tropical country, has considerable rates of ophidic envenoming, with a wide variety of venomous snakes distributed throughout the national territory, which cause around 4,000 to 7,000 accidents per year (De Sousa *et al.* 2013).

The signs of black rattlesnake (*Crotalus*

pifanorum) envenomation may vary depending on the amount of venom inoculated in the victims, the affected anatomical region and the time of evolution. The most frequent symptoms are pain, progressive oedema and nausea. Furthermore, due to its toxicity, there may be tissue damage involving the skeletal muscle system, the cardiopulmonary area, and the kidneys. The peripheral nervous system is also affected producing a pre- and postsynaptic block

in the neuromuscular plates and flaccid paralysis that can affect the respiratory muscles. Myotoxins and cardiotoxins depolarise the skeletal, cardiac and smooth muscle fibres, decreasing the performance of the heart, causing paralysis (Rengifo & Rodríguez-Acosta 2004).

Few works have referred the activity of these venoms on the adrenal gland. The significance of these glands was ignored until the mid-nineteenth century (Kloss *et al.* 1995), and it was not until the beginning of the 20th century that the hypothesis of the vital indispensability of the adrenals was confirmed (Kemp 1937), who demonstrated that bilateral adrenalectomy caused the death of the experimental animals a few hours after the intervention. Later researchers showed that only the adrenal cortical zone was essential for life (Lloyd *et al.* 2002, Solomon *et al.* 2013).

This study aims to describe the quantitative and qualitative expressions of the general ultrastructural changes occurring in the subcellular components of the adrenal gland cells of envenomed mice, emphasising the mitochondria, the Golgi apparatus, the endoplasmic reticulum and lipid inclusions, four essential structures related to the synthesis of hormones playing an important role in the homeostasis and physiological regulation of the mammalian host.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animals and venoms

Five adults *Crotalus pifanorum* snakes consisting of both sexes were captured in the field at Parmana Town, Guárico state (Venezuelan Bolivarian Republic) Latitude: 7°50'21"; Longitude: 65°45'30", and kept in captivity at the Serpentarium of the Tropical Medicine Institute of the Universidad Central de Venezuela. The black rattlesnake lives in bushes and small forests surrounded by savannah, in the warm and low areas south of Guárico state, from the Mercedes de los Llanos to the limits with Anzoátegui state (Venezuela). The snake's geographical area is characterised by average temperatures of 28°C, where there are well defined seasons: the rainy, locally called "winter", which extends from April to September; and the dry season called "summer" from October to March. Annual mean average precipitations are from 1200 to 1800 mm; relative humidity of 50 to 75% or higher in the rainy season (Pifano 1961).

Venom was obtained by allowing the snakes

to bite into a para-film® extended over a non-reusable plastic cup. The venom sample was centrifuged (500 × *g* for 10 min), and filtered through 0.45 µm filter under positive pressure. The venom was frozen at -90°C and then liophilised. The biological activity was assayed using BALB/c mice (18-22 g) purchased from the Animal House of the National Institute of Hygiene "Rafael Rangel" (Caracas, Venezuela).

Ethical statement

The experimental procedures relating to the use of live animals were carried out by qualified personnel. Venezuelan pertinent regulations as well as institutional guidelines, according to protocols approved by the Anatomic Institute of the Universidad Central de Venezuela Ethical Committee (project # 200718) and the norms obtained from the guidelines for the care and use of laboratory animals, published by the US National Institute of Health (NIH 1985) were followed.

Preparation of specimens for electron microscopy

Adult male mice were separated into a control group (n = 3) that were injected intraperitoneally (i.p.) with 0.1 mL of phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and the experimental group (n = 9) that were injected with a sublethal dose (20 µg/200 µL of PBS) of *C. pifanorum* venom. After 3, 6 and 24 h, three mice from each group were prepared for adrenal gland biopsies. The tissue removal was immediately obtained from the control and experimental mice after cervical dislocation. Samples were immediately *in situ* fixed with 3% glutaraldehyde and 1% osmium tetroxide (OsO₄) (both fixatives diluted in 320 mM PBS, pH 7.4), dehydrated in ethanol and embedded in LX-112 resin (Ladd Research Inc, USA). Ultrathin sections were stained with uranyl acetate and lead citrate and observed with a FEI Tecnai Spirit 12G2 model (FEI Company, USA) transmission electron microscope, with an accelerating voltage of 100 kV and the FEI Quanta 250 FEG microscope in STEM mode for the analysis and description of the images. The digitalisation of the micrograph images used in the descriptive study was stored with relevant information (e.g. magnification factor, type of microscope, etc.) in a computer for further study.

Numerical handling of the results

Imagine J

Morphometric measurements were made from the micrographs obtained in the thin and

thick sections using the IMAGE-J program.

Statistical analysis

ANOVA is an analysis of the variance statistical procedure that allows analysing if more than two groups differ significantly among themselves in terms of their means and variance. The procedure for comparing these values is based on the global variance observed in the groups of numerical data to be compared. Typically, the ANOVA is used to associate a probability to the conclusion that the mean of a group of scores is different from the mean of another group of scores. In this way, it was established that the ANOVA is a statistical procedure that allows analysing, if more than two groups differ significantly among themselves, in terms of their means and variance. Through the comparison, we tried to test a hypothesis of difference among more than two groups (Milton 2007).

Analysis of principal components (PCA)

The principal components analysis (PCA) consists of expressing a set of variables in a set of linear combinations of factors that are not correlated with each other. This method allowed us to represent the original data (individuals and

variables) in a space of fewer dimensions, than the original space. The estimated variables for the quantitative description of the adrenal gland were thickening of the capillary endothelium, area of capillary light, cell core area, swelling of the nuclear envelope, number of mitochondria, area of the mitochondria, number of mitochondrial cristae, number of cristae per mitochondrial unit and diameter cisternae of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum.

RESULTS

Adrenal gland changes induced by *Crotalus pifanorum* venom (Cpv) analysed by transmission electron microscopy

In the qualitative analysis from the normal adrenal cortex control, microvilli of cortical cells, the fenestrae and the thin endothelial wall, as corresponds to a normal capillary and the thin basal membrane were noticed. In the cortical cell, mitochondria with tubular cristae and moderately extracted lipid droplets were seen (Fig. 1A). A capillary was observed with erythrocytes inside and fenestrae of the non-thickened endothelium. In the cortical cell, mitochondria with osmiophilic granules and a nucleus with a narrow nuclear envelope were seen, as befits a normal cell (Fig. 1B).

Figure 1. Adrenal cortex normal control. (A) A microvilli of cortical cells (triangle) whose function is to increase the secretory activity of the gland. The fenestrae are observed (arrow); thin endothelial wall (not thickened), as corresponds to a normal capillary and the thin basement membrane (circle). In the cortical cell, mitochondria with tubular cristae (star) and a partially extracted lipid droplet (Lip) can be seen. (B) A capillary with erythrocytes (E) inside, fenestrae of the non-thickened endothelium (arrow). In the cortical cell, note mitochondria with osmiophilic granules (star) and a nucleus with a narrow nuclear envelope (arrowhead), as befits a normal cell. Micromark = 1 μ m.

After 3 h of Cpv injection, mitochondria with swollen cristae, cisternae of smooth endoplasmic

reticulum and a Weibel-Palade body were observed (Fig. 2A). Electrondense lipid droplets,

mitochondria with tubular cristae were observed. In contact with the microvilli of the cortical cell, part of the nucleus of an apparently mesenchymal cell was noticed (Fig. 2B). An endothelial cell with normal fenestrae, slightly electron-dense mitochondria and cisternae of the rough endoplasmic reticulum were seen (Fig.

2C). Cortical cells with different electron density was seen; the most electro-transparent area showed mitochondria with tubular cristae and an erythrocyte in emperipolesis, this cell looked more swollen than the electron-dense, which could indicate an alteration at the level of the plasma membrane (Fig. 2D).

Figure 2. Adrenal cortex 3 h post injection with rattlesnake *Crotalus pifanorum* venom. (A) Mitochondria with swollen cristae (stars), cisternae of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum (arrow) and a Weibel-Palade body (arrow head) were observed. (B) Electron-dense lipid droplets (LIP) mitochondria with tubular cristae (star) were observed. In contact with the microvilli (triangle) of the cortical cell, part of the nucleus (square) of an apparently mesenchymal cell was observed. (C) The endothelial cell (arrow head), normal fenestrae (oval), slightly electron-dense mitochondria (stars) and cisternae of the rough endoplasmic reticulum (arrow). (D) Cortical cells with different electron density were appreciated, the most electro-transparent shows mitochondria with tubular cristae (arrow) and an erythrocyte (E) (emperipolesis), this cell looks more swollen than the electron-dense, it could indicate an alteration at the level of the plasma membrane. Micromark = 1 μ .

After 6 h of *Cpv* injection, there was a capillary with an erythrocyte inside; normal fenestrae and a capillary lumen were seen. The left part of the section of the cortical cell presents an aspect of greater secretory activity (large amounts of organelles that participate in the secretion) than the right part of the section. Electron-dense mitochondria, lipid droplets and reduced smooth endoplasmic reticulum were observed (Fig. 3A). Two cortical cells were seen, which showed nuclei with different electron

density and variable heterochromatin content. The nucleus on the right presented a slightly swollen nuclear envelope and being the cortical cell that surrounds it, more electron-dense, which indicates more synthetic activity. Mitochondria in a degenerative process, Golgi apparatus, lipid droplets and cisternae of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum were noticed (Fig. 3B). In an altered cortical cell, we could see a nucleus with its nucleolus and nuclear envelope slightly swollen in some sites. The loss of the cyto-architecture of

the components of the cytoplasm: mitochondria, lipid droplets and swollen endoplasmic reticulum profiles were observed (Fig. 3C). Changes in mitochondria were also seen, such as the loss and

swelling of the mitochondrial cristae, an increase in the mitochondrial area and in the process of autophagy. The absence of smooth endoplasmic reticulum and lipids was also noticed (Fig. 3D).

Figure 3. Adrenal cortex 6 hours post injection with rattlesnake *Crotalus pifanorum* venom. (A) A capillary with an erythrocyte (E) inside, normal fenestrae (oval), capillary lumen (circle). The area of the section of the left cortical cell presents an aspect of greater secretory activity (greater wealth of organelles that participate in the secretion) than the right section. Electron-dense mitochondria (star), lipids droplets (Lip), smooth endoplasmic reticulum reduction (square). (B) Two cortical cells are observed which show nuclei (Nu) with different electron density and variable heterochromatin content. Note that the nucleus on the right presents a slightly swollen nuclear envelope (arrow head) and being the cortical cell that surrounds it, more electron-dense indicates more synthetic activity. Mitochondria in a degenerative process (star), Golgi apparatus (Go), lipid droplets (Lip) and cisternae of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum (arrow). (C) In an altered cortical cell we can see a nucleus (Nu) with its nucleolus (circle) and nuclear envelope in some slightly swollen sites (arrow head). Note the loss of the cytoarchitecture of the components of the cytoplasm: mitochondria (star), lipid drops (Lip) and swollen endoplasmic reticulum profiles (arrow). (D) In this micrograph, changes in mitochondria, such as the loss and swelling of the mitochondrial cristae, an increase in the mitochondrial area and in the process of autophagy (star), stand out. The absence of smooth endoplasmic reticulum (circle) and lipid droplets (Lip) is also detailed. Micromark = 1 μ m.

After 24 h of *Cpv* injection, a capillary with an erythrocyte, the separation of the fenestrae

from the capillary and thickening of the capillary endothelium were detected. In the central part of

the endothelial cell, the loss of the electron density of the cytoplasm was noticed, a nucleus peripherally cut, and mitochondria with loss of its cristae was also seen. In the neighbouring of the cortical cell, electron dense lipid droplets, lysosomes and mitochondria without mitochondrial cristae were observed (Fig. 4A). The necrosis process of a capillary was seen. The rupture of the nucleus envelope of the endothelial cell, the thickening of the capillary endothelium and the capillary lumen were observed. In the cortical cell, microvilli of

different length and thickness were noticed (Fig. 4B). Considerable changes were detected in the nucleus with a swollen nuclear envelope and empty areas that indicate a nuclear degeneration. The mitochondria were electron dense and of variable sizes, and the absence of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum was also observed (Fig. 4C). The process of necrosis of the cortical cells, loss of the mitochondrial cristae and absence of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum was detected (Fig. 4D).

Figure 4. Adrenal cortex 24 h post injection with rattlesnake *Crotalus pifanorum* venom. (A) A capillary with an erythrocyte (E), separation of the fenestrae from the capillary (oval) and thickening of the capillary endothelium (arrow head) is observed. In the central part of the endothelial cell, the loss of the electronic density of the cytoplasm is noticed (triangle), a nucleus peripherally cut (square), and mitochondria with loss of its cristae (arrow). In the neighbouring cortical cell are observed electron dense lipid drops (Lip), lysosome (circle) and mitochondria without mitochondrial cristae (star). (B) The process of necrosis of a capillary is seen, where alterations are described such as: The rupture of the nucleus (Nu) envelope of the endothelial cell (arrow), thickening of the capillary endothelium (circle) and the capillary lumen (square). In the cortical cell, microvilli of different length and thickness (triangle) are observed. (C) Considerable changes are observed in the nucleus (Nu) with rupture of its nuclear envelope (triangle) and empty areas that indicate a nuclear degeneration. The mitochondria are electron dense and of variable sizes (star) the absence of the smooth reticulum (circle) is also observed. (D) The process of necrosis of the cortical cells, loss of the mitochondrial cristae (star) and absence of the smooth reticulum (circle) is appreciated. Micromark = 1 μ m.

Table 1 shows the quantitative analysis of the adrenal gland after injections with *Cpv* at 3, 6 and 24 h. These analyses consisted of thickening of the capillary endothelium in different subcellular components of the adrenal gland,

capillary lumen and nucleus area, thickening of nuclear envelope, number of mitochondria, area of the mitochondria, number of mitochondrial cristae, and diameter of the cisternae of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum.

Table 1. Quantitative analysis.

<i>C. pifanorum</i> venom (Time h)	Thickening of the capillary endothelium (measured in μm)	Capillary lumen (measured in μm)	Nucleus area (measured in μm)	Thickening of nuclear envelope (measured in μm)	Number of mitochondria	Area of the mitochondria (measured in μm)	Number of mitochondrial cristae	Diameter of the cisternae of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum (measured in μm)
Control	Mean \pm SD							
3	0.31 \pm 0.013	8.58 \pm 0.08	17.28 \pm 0.40	14.10 \pm 0.13	1.75 \pm 0.117	0.14 \pm 0.0089	27.46 \pm 0.74	0.011 \pm 0.0009
6	0.31 \pm 0.013	8.48 \pm 0.08	16.93 \pm 0.36	14.00 \pm 0.14	1.78 \pm 0.121	0.13 \pm 0.0082	26.21 \pm 1.13	0.009 \pm 0.0008
24	0.29 \pm 0.014	8.78 \pm 0.13	17.28 \pm 0.42	14.10 \pm 0.14	1.78 \pm 0.127	0.14 \pm 0.0086	26.62 \pm 0.91	0.007 \pm 0.0005
Venom	Mean \pm SD							
3	0.33 \pm 0.012	8.60 \pm 0.17	15.73 \pm 0.27	13.98 \pm 0.29	1.53 \pm 0.080	0.15 \pm 0.010	28.38 \pm 0.75	0.054 \pm 0.0088
6	0.65 \pm 0.020	9.13 \pm 0.19	13.78 \pm 0.70	15.50 \pm 0.14	1.28 \pm 0.101	0.37 \pm 0.017	14.85 \pm 0.94	0.186 \pm 0.0066
24	0.73 \pm 0.019	10.55 \pm 0.18	7.10 \pm 0.48	18.80 \pm 0.22	0.33 \pm 0.075	0.50 \pm 0.031	3.95 \pm 0.44	0.271 \pm 0.0063

To evaluate the effect of thickening of the capillary endothelium, capillary lumen, nucleus area, thickening of nuclear envelope, number of mitochondria, area of the mitochondria, number of mitochondrial cristae and diameter of the cisternae of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) of two factors at 95% confidence was developed in which it was found that there were significant differences for changes in the treatments (factor 1) $P = 0.00$ and significant difference for times (factor 2) $P = 0.00$, with an interaction of $P = 0.00$. The table shows the trends of the means and standard errors for the 4 treatments over time, obtained during the study of the above parameters. SD: standard deviation.

DISCUSSION

The adrenal cortex, as its designation indicates surrounds the adrenal medulla. Its role is to regulate metabolic components with the production of mineralocorticoids and glucocorticoids that include aldosterone and cortisol. The adrenal cortex is also a secondary site of androgen synthesis. The basic structure of adrenal cortex cells is typical of steroid-producing cells. They have few rough endoplasmic reticulum, but abundant smooth endoplasmic reticulum, where numerous lipid inclusions are observed. Additionally, mitochondria are usually rounded with tubular cristae (Kloss *et al.* 1995).

Depending on the cell types and the function

they perform, the adrenal cortex has three different layers: *a*) The glomerular zone, which is formed by a group of small and poorly defined cells while the fascicular cells are larger and form long cords arranged radially with respect to the medulla (Lloyd *et al.* 2002). These cells produce mineralocorticoids, especially aldosterone. *b*) The fascicular zone, the cells of this zone, stimulated by the adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) and is responsible for the production of glucocorticoids (Lloyd *et al.* 2002). *c*) Reticular zone, this is the most internal, it is formed by a network of short strands of cells with interdigitised capillaries. These cells have less smooth endoplasmic reticulum and fewer lipid inclusions than the cells of the fascicular zone, but more lysosomes and lipofuscin granules. The mitochondria tend to be more elongated and have both short and long tubular ridges. This area is considered to be the site where the dead cells of the adrenal cortex lodge (Kloss *et al.* 1995). Cells in the reticular zone produce a secondary source of testosterone, dihydrotestosterone (DHT), androstenedione, and dehydroepiandrosterone (DHEA); hormones that increase muscle mass, stimulate cell growth and help the development of secondary sexual characteristics (Solomon *et al.* 2013).

This study aims to describe the sequence of general ultrastructural changes caused by *Cpv* that occur in the cells of the adrenal gland, emphasising the mitochondria, the Golgi apparatus and the endoplasmic reticulum and lipid inclusions, four important structures related

to the synthesis of hormones that, in addition, play an important role in the homeostasis and physiological regulation of the mammal's host.

Adrenotoxic events triggered by *Cpv*, seen in the clinical signs of the experimental mice, suggested that the mice adrenal glands were particularly vulnerable to this venom. Mice developed irritable and aggressive conducts instantly after injections and then they initiated to vomit, displaying weakness evident by slow, lethargic and exhausted behaviour, followed by deep faintness. Finally, respiratory paralysis occurred, mainly due to the neurotoxic activity, but this did not disregard the acute adrenocortical insufficiency, which could have also been the result of the animals' death. Signal of acute adrenal damage was established by circulatory collapse, which is regarded as anarduous respiration, shock and coma. Death frequently happened after a few hours, which could have been caused by adrenal insufficiency (Waterhouse 1911). As it is known, primary adrenal insufficiency can be a result of adrenal gland destruction by either direct or indirect actions of phospholipases A₂, metallo- and serine protease agents, which cause haemorrhages or coagulation disorders, for instance those caused by some natural toxins, such as in bee (*Apis mellifera*) (Rodríguez-Acosta *et al.* 2003, 2004) and scorpion (*Tityus discrepans*) venoms (Rodríguez-Acosta *et al.* 2000).

Three hours post *Cpv* injections, the micrograph showed intense damages at the adrenal cortex, where the cortical cells with different electron density (being the most electro-transparent) was noticed. Mitochondria with tubular cristae and an erythrocyte in emperipolesis were also observed (this phenomenon represents the active penetration of one cell by another, which remains with an intact normal structure, differing from phagocytosis in that the engulfed cell is damaged by the protective action of lysosomal enzymes). Endothelial cells with normal fenestrae looks more oedematized than the electro-dense, suggesting a modification on the plasma membrane, showing slightly electro-dense mitochondria and cisternae of the rough endoplasmic reticulum. The lesions detected in mitochondria and endoplasmic reticulum might be enough to produce deficiency of steroid synthesis. These effects advise that altered degrees of adrenal dysfunction could be present in mice presenting the clinical expression of envenoming defined above.

The Weibel-Palade bodies found here represent secretory organelles used for post-

synthesis storage in endothelial cells that can, very rapidly, be triggered, by animals envenomed with a strong haemostatic venom, to discharge their contents consisting of a variety of bioactive molecules essential to haemostasis and inflammation, vascular tonicity and angiogenesis (Metcalf *et al.* 2008).

Six hours post *Cpv* injections, mitochondria was observed in a degenerative condition, smooth endoplasmic reticulum cisternae and lipid droplets were reduced, oedema, and a more electron-dense nucleus envelope was developed, all an indication of the devastating effects that the venom toxins can cause. The loss of the cyto-architecture of the mitochondria in an autophagy process, which showed an increase in their area with loss and swelling of the cristae, and also the observation of swollen endoplasmic reticulum profiles, surrounded by lipid droplets must definitely generate serious alterations, in the activity and function of the different subcellular elements, stimulating a cell dysfunction and could explain the acute clinical picture presented by the experimental animals.

Twenty four hours post *Cpv* injections, a capillary with the separation of the fenestrae and a necrotic condition were seen. The nuclear envelope of the endothelial cell was ruptured, and thickening of the capillary endothelium and the capillary lumen were observed. In the capillary beds, where metalloprotease toxins are expected to apply their robust influences on barrier integrity, there is an important interaction between endothelial cells and pericytes, which is principally significant in preserving an intact blood barrier. Important changes were noticed in the nucleus with rupture of its nuclear envelope and empty areas that indicate a nuclear degeneration.

The electron density of the mitochondria observed at 6 and 24 h, occurs under circumstances where respiration and/or oxidative phosphorylation are repressed, which evidently reduced intensities of adenosine triphosphate (ATP) production. If the condensed conformation is sustained, substantial damage to the inner membrane take place, an alteration that also undoubtedly associates with loss of the mitochondrial membrane potential (Trump & Berezsky 1992).

The adrenal gland is a highly vascularised organ, and the endothelial dysfunction, hyperaemia, oedema, and haemorrhage are vital features related with severe inflammation-associated damages. Furthermore, adding data (Jahangir-Hekmat *et al.* 2004, Sánchez *et al.*

2018) showed that endothelial dysfunction and adrenal haemorrhage enhance the inflammation related adrenal insufficiency. Toxins also cause oxidative stress and overproduction of nitric oxide in adrenal glands, thereby leading to adrenocortical insufficiency. The adrenal steroidogenic cells are principally susceptible to oxidative stress (Meimaridou *et al.* 2018). In the adrenocortical cells, extreme sums of molecular oxygen are consumed not only for aerobic energy production (ATP synthesis) in the mitochondria but also for steroid biosynthesis. During this biosynthesis is created reactive oxygen, for instance oxygen-centred free radicals and peroxides as by-products of oxidative metabolism (Wang *et al.* 2015).

Once the qualitative observations of the alterations had been established, it was equally important to demonstrate or detail these alterations at a quantitative level, which allows to obtain greater objectivity and to explain the behaviour amongst the time course of venom administration. In this sense, the alterations were quantified by means of a morphometric analysis by corroborating if the action of the venom, at different times, had statistical significance.

Alterations on the microvasculature of the adrenal gland were described, where the thickening of the endothelium and the area of the capillary lumen were measured, this is represented in Table 1. It is remarkable that the treatment at 3 h after inoculation was not significantly different compared with the control. However, when observing the alterations at 6 and 24 h, it can be seen that the *Cpv* was statistically significant with the control. This alteration corresponds to the time previously described (adrenal cortex 3 and 6 hours post injection with *Cpv*) in the qualitative part where the destruction of the endothelium was observed (Figs. 5A and B). Alterations of the endothelium are always involved with the occurrence of haemorrhage after snake envenoming (Araujo & Rivas 1999, Rengifo & Rodríguez-Acosta 2004).

In another variable, the capillary lumen, at six hours after *Cpv* injection, was not statistically significant compared with the control (Table 1). Although at 24 h, a kinetic of temporary increase associated with a possible dilatation of the capillary respect to the control was observed (Table 1).

Regarding the nucleus area at 3 and 6 h after envenomation, it was not noticeably affected, but at 24 h the nucleus area decreased nearly 50% (Table 1). The construction of enzymatic proteins by the cell is regulated in the nucleus. To do this,

it uses mRNA (messenger RNA), which is in charge for carrying information to the ribosomal RNA in the cytoplasm. There, the synthesis of enzymatic proteins that control the metabolic processes takes place. Furthermore, in the nucleus are the chromosomes, which contain all the genetic information of the individual, which is passed on to the daughter cells during cell division. A nucleus damaged by apoptosis or necrosis leads to cell death.

Concerning the thickening of the nuclear envelope, only a discreet change was observed at 24 h. The nuclear pores located in the nuclear envelope allow the passage of RNA, ribosomes, proteins, carbohydrates, lipids, etc., to the cytoplasm.

Relating to the number of mitochondria, a subtle change was observed at 3 and 6 h; however at 24 h, an intense decrease was observed. As it is known its main function is to provide the necessary energy to carry out cellular respiration (Wang *et al.* 2015).

In the mitochondrial cristae, numerous chemical reactions of importance to the cell occur, such as cellular respiration, electron transport, oxidative phosphorylation, and protein transport. The cristae form a membranous system that connects with the inner membrane of the mitochondria in different parts to facilitate the transport of metabolites and organic compounds to various parts of the mitochondria (Wang *et al.* 2015). When observing the alterations at 6 and 24 h, it can be seen that the venom of the *Cpv* was statistically significant compared with the control. At 24 h an intense decrease in the amount was noticed (Table 1).

The diameter of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum cisternae was dramatically increased from the early 3 h, reaching its maximum at 24 h. This subcellular structure is responsible for the synthesis of molecules and the transport of substances. One of its functions is to deliver the proteins synthesised to the Golgi apparatus, which will transform and send them to the rest of the organisms. The venom of *Cpv* produced a strong reduction of the smooth endoplasmic reticulum (Figs. 4 and 5), but the diameter of the cistern was intensely increased at 6 and 24 h after envenomation (Table 1).

Finally, many of the pathogenic activities on the adrenal glands by *Cpv* were possibly due to the presence of proteolytic enzymes such as metalloproteases and phospholipases A₂ that disrupt basal membranes structures (Ownby & Geren 1987) and are also described in other

Crotalus species. To our knowledge, these results characterise the first ultrastructural description of severe mice adrenal gland damage triggered by *Cpv*.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Funding for the research was provided by grants from the CDCH, UCV PG: 09-8760-2013, Caracas, Venezuela (Dr. Alexis Rodríguez-Acosta) and NCRR/BMRG, Viper Resource Grant #S 8P40OD01960-10 3P40OD01096-10S1 (NNTRC, Texas A & M University-Kingsville), and the Robert A. Welch Foundation Department Grant #AC-0006 (TAMUK-Department of Chemistry) (Dr. Elda E. Sánchez).

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